

Understanding Stator Current and Frame Vibrations for Electrical Machine Maintenance: An Educational Approach Using FEA-Assisted Test Bench

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Abstract—Rotating electrical machine maintenance is present in engineering education curricula in many institutions around the globe. Vibration monitoring represents a widespread methodology for electrical rotating machinery monitoring. However, the multi-physical nature of vibration monitoring presents a complex learning scenario, encompassing concepts from both mechanical and electrical engineering domains. This article introduces a practical learning methodology aimed at comprehensively addressing the electromechanical link between stator current and frame vibration. To this aim, a virtual Finite Element Analysis (FEA) model is utilized to link phase current signals with airgap radial forces acting in the stator. The spectrum of the radial force in the frequency domain is correlated with the measured radial frame vibration in the real machine specimen. In this way, the electromechanical link of electrical machine vibration monitoring is elucidated in a practical manner.

Index Terms—Training, fault diagnosis, vibration monitoring, AC machines

I. INTRODUCTION

In various economic sectors such as automotive, energy, and industry, there is a growing focus on electrifying numerous applications. While rotating electrical machines are reliable for electromechanical energy conversion, they are still prone to failures, presenting a significant maintenance challenge [1]. The consequences of machine failures can be severe, leading to substantial economic costs and risking operational safety. Traditionally, maintenance has been carried out periodically or reactively, waiting until a failure occurs. However, new maintenance strategies are emerging to address the limitations of these approaches. Predictive maintenance, also known as condition-based maintenance, allows for continuous monitoring of machinery, reducing downtime and preventing critical

failures that could compromise safety [2]. This monitoring involves gathering and analyzing various physical parameters such as vibrations, temperature, and phase current using appropriate tools. Currently, there is significant academic and industrial research focused on advancing predictive maintenance techniques.

Works on electrical machinery maintenance education are found in literature, where the authors highlight the presence of maintenance courses in different engineering curricula [3]. These courses deal with the monitoring via frame vibrations, which represents a widespread industrial technique to detect and diagnose several faults [4]. The nature of mechanical signals (e.g., vibrations) in electrical machines poses an inherent multi-physical nature, including concepts of mechanical and electrical engineering. Thus, the understanding of electromagnetically excited vibrations for diagnosis purposes poses an educational challenge. Given the complexity of related concepts, a purely theoretical approach should not be encouraged, and practical teaching experiences should be provided instead. In this regard, practical sessions have proven to enable scientific discovery and inquiry-based learning [5], fostering a wide range of skills such as communication, teamwork, ethics, and encouraging information acquisition [6]. The above, aiming to support learning in lectures by enhancing student understanding of theoretical concepts.

The present work introduces a methodology to improve the comprehension of electromagnetically induced vibrations in induction machines. This is achieved via practical sessions including both FEA modelling and laboratory signal acquisition and analysis. The work is organized as follows. Section II describes the education context of the proposed practical session. Section III poses the main theoretical concepts. Section IV presents the developed FEA framework and the targeted induction machine specimen. Section V presents the experimental test bench, and section VI analyzes the results. Section VII summarizes the learning objectives and closes the work.

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II. EDUCATION CONTEXT

The conceived practical workshop is enclosed within different Master courses in Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV). Prof. Antonino-Daviu is the current responsible for different subjects including electrical machinery maintenance concepts. The first course is named "*Maintenance of Electrical Machines and Installations*", which is included within an official UPV master named "*Master on Maintenance Engineering*". The second subject is named "*Electric Traction and Electrical Machine Technology*", included in the official UPV program "*Master of Science in Industrial Engineering*".

The mentioned courses encompass topics related to monitoring the condition of electric motors. Topics covered include analyzing motor currents, conducting partial discharge analysis, performing offline tests to assess insulation condition, stray-flux data, among other techniques. These span from traditional maintenance practices, like corrective and breakdown maintenance, to advanced preventive and predictive methods. The latter are examined in depth, particularly focusing on modern electrical monitoring techniques. Vibration monitoring applied to electrical machines is sometimes neglected due to its inner complexity and the mechanical nature of such signals. Nevertheless, the present workshop is engineered to bridge the knowledge gap between the mechanical and electrical worlds in the frame of education on electrical machine maintenance.

III. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The present section is intended to set the main theoretical concepts prior to the workshop execution in a summarized way. Basic knowledge about induction machine working principles and constructive elements is assumed as a prerequisite. The presented formulation is based on a well-known reference book in the field of noise and vibrations of electrical machines [7]. The explanation of concepts is separated in electromagnetic and mechanical domains respectively.

Let's assume an ideal system and a perfectly sinusoidal three-phase voltage wave exiting the stator winding. Depending on the dynamic model of induction machine including stator and rotor resistances and inductances, stator phase current flows through the stator windings and rotor current is induced within the rotor bars [8]. Stator and rotor current frequencies are related through the slip, which is a basic induction machine parameter. Currents flowing within the stator and rotor conductors create an air-gap magneto-motive force, which depends on the conductor distribution along the machine periphery and on the properties of the input wave ($mmf(t, \theta)$). The air-gap geometry includes stator and rotor slots, while the ferromagnetic material is saturated along some sections of the air-gap. These effects are accounted by defining the air-gap permeance function, which can be assumed as solely dependent on the air-gap angle ($\Lambda_g(\theta)$). By multiplying the magneto-motive force and the permeance, the two-dimensional airgap flux density wave is obtained:

$$b(t, \theta) = [mmf_{st}(t, \theta) + mmf_{rot}(t, \theta)] \Lambda_g(\theta) \quad (1)$$

Fig. 1. Relationships between electromagnetic magnitudes for radial force density computation

where the two magneto-motive force waves are separated into stator and rotor respectively. The air-gap magnetic flux density wave can be separated into tangential and radial components. The radial component predominantly contributes to the air-gap Radial Force Density (RFD) function. According to Maxwell stress tensor approach, the RFD wave can be approximated as:

$$F_r(t, \theta) \approx \frac{b_r^2(t, \theta)}{2\mu_0} \quad (2)$$

where $b_r(t, \theta)$ represents the radial air-gap flux density wave and μ_0 is the vacuum permeability. Figure 1 shows a comprehensive flow chart where all electromagnetic waves are inter-related.

Electromagnetic radial forces excite the stator teeth creating vibrations in the housing surface. Nevertheless, the stator including windings and the housing constitute mechanical elements with a non-ideal vibrating transfer path. The mechanical transfer path amplifies or damps the vibrating forces depending on a transfer function $H(f)$, which depends on the mechanical system mass, stiffness, and damping. This mechanical transfer function can be assimilated to the electrical domain, where mass, stiffness, and damping are compared with inductances, capacitances, and resistances of a RLC resonant circuit. The mechanical transfer path can be broadly estimated by utilizing analytical methods [7], and FEA [9]. Nevertheless, the most common and accurate methodology is to perform experimental modal analysis to estimate the mechanical system parameters and thus, obtain the mechanical transfer path between excitation and acquisition point [10]. The problem is simplified from a machine diagnosis perspective, where limited amount of housing points are available to perform vibration acquisition due to the presence of cooling fins, connection boxes, etc. Thus, the acceleration is sampled in single points, where the radial force excitation and the acceleration measurement are related by an unknown transfer function:

$$\ddot{x}(t) = H(f)F_r(t) \quad (3)$$

where $\ddot{x}(t)$ represents the acceleration measured in the sampling point, and $F_r(t)$ is the electromagnetic exciting force in radial direction. Note that the single-point acquisition of vibration eliminates the dependence on the air-gap position θ . Figure 2 shows an overview of the most important theoretical concepts to bridge electrical and mechanical domains.

Fig. 2. Description of relationships between electrical input and mechanical measured output

IV. MACHINE SPECIMEN AND ELECTROMAGNETIC FEA MODEL

The machine specimen selected for electromagnetic and mechanical assessment is a 4-pole commercial IE3 1.1 kW squirrel-cage induction machine, the main data of which are summarized in Table I.

A 2D FEA model in Ansys Electronics Desktop platform was devised to evaluate relevant performance indicators of the machine, as presented schematically in Figure 3. A high density mesh was created in the airgap, slot opening and rotor bar areas to correctly obtain the transient and steady-state machine response. The proposed 2D model was validated by means of experimental testing at rated conditions, as described in Table II. A good agreement may be appreciated in terms of rated performance, and current response was further verified

TABLE I
MAIN DATA OF THE SELECTED 1.1 kW COMMERCIAL IM SPECIMEN

Symbol	Variable	Value	Unit
P	Number of pole pairs	2	—
Q_s	Number of stator slots	36	—
Q_r	Number of rotor slots	28	—
D_{so}	Stator outer diameter	135.0	mm
D_{si}	Stator inner diameter	85.4	mm
D_{ro}	Rotor outer diameter	85.0	mm
δ	Air-gap length	0.4	mm
h_s	Slot height	13.0	mm
w_s	Tooth width	3.9	mm
N	Number of turns per coil	55	—
θ_{skew}	Rotor skew angle	10	deg
ω_r	Rated speed	1440	rpm
τ_r	Rated torque	7.33	Nm
η_r	Rated efficiency	86	%
$\cos\phi_r$	Rated power factor	0.78	—

Fig. 3. 2D FE model devised to represent the electromagnetic and mechanical response of a 1.1 kW IE3 commercial machine. Each quarter of this figure presents a different feature of the cross-section of the specimen: the real machine (lower-left), the modelled geometry (lower-right), the considered mesh (upper-right) and the flux density distribution (upper-left)

by assessing 12 different operating points at different motor speed and line voltage values.

In order to evaluate radial force density by means of the proposed model, a circumferential path was created in the airgap, from which flux density values were obtained both in space and time. Transient mechanical simulation is considered to this end, starting the machine from rest and imposing a variable load torque depending on the desired operation conditions. Simulation time step is set to 0.5 ms in order to obtain relevant information from the harmonic analysis of electromagnetic signals up to 1000 Hz, and 10 s of steady state were recorded to provide a frequency spacing of 0.1 Hz when assessing harmonic content of signal waveforms. Nevertheless, students are allowed to change the selection of time step and total registered time, since it has a direct influence on the assessment of relevant signals.

Aiming to showcase to learners the relationship between the easily measurable vibrations and the complex formulation of radial force density wave in the machine airgap, a simulation is devised to extract the RFD from the circumferential path created in the machine airgap. As an example, Figure 4(a)

TABLE II
PERFORMANCE COMPARISON BETWEEN THE DEVELOPED FE MODEL AND EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Symbol	Variable	FE (2D)	Experimental
τ_r	Rated torque	7.46 Nm	7.33 Nm
I_s	Stator line current	2.2 A	2.4 A
P_{out}	Output power	1.13 kW	1.1 kW
η_r	Rated efficiency	89.1%	84.1%
$\cos\phi_r$	Rated power factor	0.766	0.78

Fig. 4. Electromagnetic variables estimated through FEA from a commercial IM, (a) Steady-state Airgap flux density and radial force density estimated in an equidistant point between a stator tooth and rotor surface; (b) Steady-state stator phase current, (c) Transient airgap flux density and radial force density; (d) Transient stator phase current

and (b) depict the flux density signal obtained from the 2D FE simulation after the first 4 seconds of steady state, as well as the RFD waveform resulting from post-computation of flux density signals as per (3). Moreover, Figure 4(c) and (d) present the current and RFD waveforms of start-up transient. From obtained signals, a diagnosis-oriented assessment can be performed and presented to the students, taking into account i) the harmonic content of the RFD by means of conventional Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) tools in steady state, ii) the evolution of the RFD frequency spectrum in transient operation; and iii) the relationship between the observed physical quantities and vibration/forces generation. It should be noted that the 2D FE simulation was created in tight agreement with the actual 1.1 kW machine specimen, and that the devised simulation set is bundled in such a way that students can interact with relevant data of the machine and focus the applicability of this tool to specific learning outcomes. Particularly, dimensional data of the 2D model are locked, and interaction is oriented towards changing the motor inertia, load torque, supply voltage and simulation settings such as time step and total simulation time. Since simulation environment is risk-free and allows a significant repeatability degree, the simulation can be used for assessing a healthy machine, and be further extended to evaluate bar breakage, eccentricity and other related faults if desired.

V. EXPERIMENTAL TEST-BENCH AND ACQUISITION

The test-bench for data acquisition, as sketched in Figure 5, is formed by the induction machine under test coupled via flexible mechanical coupling to a 3.3 kW DC generator, which supply a resistive load for power dissipation. The induction machine is directly connected to the grid and thus, fed at mains frequency 50 Hz and 400 V line-to-line. The imposed resistive

Fig. 5. Test-bench and student interface description

Fig. 6. Electromagnetic and vibration signals obtained through experimental testing of the commercial IM, (a) Steady-state vibration signal; (b) Steady-state stator phase current, (c) Transient vibration signal; (d) Transient stator phase current

torque is controlled by varying the DC generator field current. The load point is set by monitoring the shaft speed via laser manual tachometer. Acceleration is acquired at a single point located in the induction machine drive-end attached via tack-it adhesive. A wave recorder is utilized to simultaneously acquire the vibration and current signals, which are processed off-line by the students after performing the experimental campaign. For security reasons, the students interactions are limited to two auto-transformers to control the supply voltage of the induction machine and the DC generator field circuit. The wave recorder interface and ampere/voltage meter readings are available for student interaction as well.

The experiment is performed in several steps to acquire both steady-state and transient signals. Students should be grouped to perform the experiments in the test-bench in groups of minimum two members. The motor is initially fed at rated voltage with no-excitation in the DC generator field voltage. The first step consists of increasing the DC generator field excitation to reach the shaft nominal speed (i.e., 1440 rpm for the specimen under test). To this aim, the shaft speed, resistive load current meter should be monitored while adjusting the autotransformer

of the DC field excitation. Then, a single phase current and accelerometer signals are acquired synchronously via wave recorder. After capturing the steady-state signals, the main supply is switched off completely stopping the motor. The last step is to capture the signals during the motor transient. To this aim, the variable autotransformer is adjusted to its 50% value to elongate the motor-start up evolution. Finally, the main supply is switched back on to capture the motor start-up. The process is repeated several times to have a significant amount of data to perform further analysis. Note that faulty conditions are not implemented to avoid hazardous environments during the laboratory sessions. Figure 6 shows an example of acquired vibration and current signals both during steady state and start-up transient.

VI. COMPARISON BETWEEN FEA AND EXPERIMENTS

From the devised learning tools, a comprehensive analysis of electromagnetic phenomena and their relationship with mechanical vibrations of the machine is performed. Basic scripts for signal processing including the classic FFT and a time-frequency Short Time Fourier Transform (STFT) are provided to the students. Figure 7 shows the frequency spectrum of both the RFD wave and vibration signals (i.e., FEA-acquired and experimental based respectively). The differences between mechanical (e.g., rotating frequency f_r multiples) and electromagnetic components are analyzed in the vibration spectrum. Then, the presence of electromagnetic components such as twice line frequency component ($2f_s$) and Principal Slot Harmonics (PSH) is closely linked to their presence in the RFD spectrum. In the case of PSH, these are slip dependent and are given by [11]:

$$PSH_{\pm\nu} = f_s \left(\frac{Q_r}{P} (1 - s) \pm \nu \right) \quad (4)$$

Fig. 7. Relevant steady-state tools to analyze vibration and forces phenomena and their relationship with internal electromagnetic quantities; RFD spectrum, from which relevant harmonic content can be identified, related to machine vibrations; (a) FFT of force density wave obtained from FE results; (b) FFT of vibration signal captured experimentally

where s is the slip, Q_r represents the number of rotor slots, P is the number of pole pairs and ν represents an even integer (i.e., $\nu = 0, 2, 4, 6, \dots$). It is recommended to perform a preliminary computation of these harmonics taking into account the parameters provided in Table I. The main outcomes of this analysis are the importance of the mechanical transfer function $H(f)$ and the agreement between FEA and experimental measurements in steady-state conditions.

Figure 8 shows the transient evolution for both simulated RFD wave and the measured vibration signal. The main focus is placed around slip dependent electromagnetic evolutions, where the PSH_{+2} dominates the experimental results. The simulated RFD presents increased number of components which are mechanically damped when acquiring the vibration signals. In addition, the initial shock during experimental measurement clearly blurs the initial part of the transient time-frequency map. This high energy shock hinders the identification of electromagnetic signature during the start-up transient evolution. The main conclusions of the transient study are the qualitative evaluation of time evolving and constant harmonic components over time as well as the damping and initial shock influence on this evaluation.

Fig. 8. Relevant transient tools to analyze vibration and forces phenomena and their relationship with internal electromagnetic quantities (RFD); (a) TF map of force density wave obtained from FE results; (b) TF map of vibration signal captured experimentally

VII. CLOSURE

The present manuscript presents a workflow to educate engineers on the multi-physics nature of fault diagnosis of electrical machines via vibration signals. This is achieved by utilizing a FEA-assisted experimental test-bench where the links between the virtual and experimental results are easily displayed. The present methodology includes the understanding and FEA simulation of an induction motor, which is available for further experimental testing. In this way, the proposed workflow aims that students can easily link the electromagnetic signature of air-gap magnetic waves with measured vibration signals in the test-bench, aiming to improve specific learning objectives. In addition, the presented methodology serves as demonstrator of the Digital Twin concept, broadly present in nowadays industrial environments.

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